

Acousmatic, invisible, ontology

Jean-Louis Di Santo

SCRIME, Bordeaux

Jean-Louis.Di-Santo@wanadoo.fr

Abstract

Acousmatic music was born from the philosophical concept of “epoché” that means that the existence of the world doesn’t matter and that the subject pays attention to his own world’s perceptions. The epoché gave the concept of reduced listening. Besides, music and sounds are invisible and acousmatic means hearing without seeing the cause of the sound. This is possible by recording sounds. All of this implies the abolition of the distinction between inner and outer. For these reasons, acousmatic music has a deep relation to invisible and particularly to invisible inside Being.

This paper aims at analyzing the mechanisms implied by this invisibility and the philosophical consequences of these mechanisms, related to the onto-logic analysis of the being by Martin Heidegger, and aims at highlighting the very close connection between the acousmatic music and Being. Acousmatic music, born from phenomenology, will find a strong echo in the theories developed by Heidegger in *Being and time*, and can be considered as a particularly “existential” art.

1. Introduction

Acousmatic music was born from the philosophical concept of “epoché” (ἐποχή). It comes from the German philosopher Edmund Husserl, and designs the suspension of the all assumptions about the existence of an external world. That means that the subject pays attention to his own world’s perceptions. In this way, the existence of an external world is put aside. Pierre Schaeffer used this notion to conceive the concept of reduced listening, to determine the perceptive qualities of sound. However, it is interesting to notice that the word ἐποχή was used by ancient Greek philosophers (school of skepticism) and was meaning “suspension of judgment” and “withholding of assent”.

Besides, music and sounds are invisible. Moreover acousmatic means hearing without seeing the cause of the sound. This is possible by recording and replaying them: acousmatic music has a reinforced link with invisible.

For these two reasons, acousmatic music has a deep relation to invisible and to invisible inside Being. This paper aims at analyzing the mechanisms implied by this invisibility and the philosophical consequences of these mechanisms, related to the onto-logic analysis of the being by Martin Heidegger, and aims at highlighting the particularly close connection between the acousmatic music and Being.

2. From recording to Dasein (Being-there)

Usually the musical performance is dependent on visible musicians and instruments. In this case, many invisibilities contained on the music are veiled and there is a contradiction between the visible matter that is the cause of the music, and the music itself that is invisible. But the possibility to fix sounds on a support brings many important consequences. François Bayle called these sounds *i-sons* (image of sounds). He wrote:

“The image [of sound] will be built from the central notion of double disconnection: the one physically done by the arrangement of other causes, following a law of simulation – and the psychological one which detect the index of a simulacra, of an interpretation, of a sign.”¹

We can a little bit more detail these disconnections:

2.1. Double disconnection from the body

The presence of musicians on stage establishes a link between the invisible music and the visible body and instruments. The musicians gestures are showing the straight link with the sonic rhythms they are producing. In acousmatic music, performing musicians disappear, and their body with them.

The body is also present by the pulsation, generally associated to physiological actions: walking, breathe, heart²... Even if regular rhythms can be found sometimes in acousmatic music, generally the pulsation – the beat - disappears. There is no more reference to the body.

2.2. Temporal, spatial and actantial disengagement (Greimas 1993)

In instrumental music, the sounds are produced by a musician here and there, the fixed sounds were produced in another time, in another place by another actant.

“... a creative split, on one hand, from the subject, from the place and from the time of the enunciation, and, on the other hand, from the actantial, spatial and temporal representation of the utterance”³

This “creative split” is specific to language and signs, and the invisible is spread in the bliss that separates the enunciation from the representation, the invisibility of that which was visible but whose only recorded trace remains, and which drains in its wake other invisibilities since it has become a sign and symbol. That is the mark of consciousness. This drives us to the following point.

1 “...l’image [de son] s’établira à partir de la notion centrale de double disjonction : celle physiquement produite par l’agencement d’autres causes, selon une loi de simulation – et celle psychologique qui décèle l’indice d’un simulacre, une interprétation, un signe.” François Bayle, *Musique acousmatique, propositions... positions*, Buchet/Chastel, Paris, 1993p 83

2 Friederich Hegel links rhythm to geometry and to spirit (“the beat proceeds from the spirit alone, far more than do the regular fixed magnitudes of architecture...”, *Aesthetics, Lecture on fine arts*, Vol II, p. 916), but he admits that the body can “beat time” (p. 906). Body and spirit are not mutually exclusive.

3 “... une schizie créatrice, d’une part, du sujet, du lieu et du temps de l’énonciation, et, de l’autre, de la représentation actantielle, spatiale et temporelle de l’énoncé.” Algirdas Julien Greimas, Joseph Courtés, *Dictionnaire raisonné du langage*, Hachette supérieur, Paris, 1993, p. 79

2.3. Disconnection from the causes and the context in which the sounds appear

Acousmatic music owes its name to the causes of sound production that become invisible, even when they remain recognizable. But François Bayle goes further: “Any figurative sound object is in any case excessively abstract; when it is abs-tract, that is, taken from its context.”⁴ The original context disappears and entails in its annihilation beings and objects related to its existence, that is, the real conditions of its production. This double dis-junction implies a dis-junction of matter, whether it be that of sound objects or that of the context, as well as the causes that built it. This double dis-junction, this abs-traction from causes and context, causes the consciousness of a «simulacra», exposes other and deeper causes, and reveals the symbolic dimension which, by the withdrawal of primitive matter and by the play of the “set-for”, contains all the invisible. These invisible concern as well internal world than external world: as invisible, the difference between them vanishes – becomes invisible, one can say.

2.4. Consequences

The totality of these mechanisms throws many things visible into the invisible: the other’s body and the material conditions of production of sound, that is visible signs of external world and of otherness. These conceptual and technical origins converge towards the abolition, in the consciousness, of the distinction between inner and outer. Hegel already noticed this abolition concerning the music:

“...[the medium of] sound proves to be more akin to the inner simple essence of a subject matter than the sensuous hitherto considered, because] instead of being fixed in spatial figures and acquiring stability as the variety of things separated or juxtaposed in space it has rather assigned to it the ideal sphere of *time*, and therefore it does not reach the difference between what is simply inner and its corporeal concrete appearance and shape.”⁵

Hegel is talking about concert music. However, using Hegelian Dialectic, we can say: the music is invisible. But the concert music, showing musician and instruments, is the negation of this invisibility. Acousmatic music, being the negation of this negation, is the sublation of the music from this point of view. Thus, in acousmatic music, there is already no difference between inner and “corporeal concrete appearance and shape” because concrete appearance has already disappeared. Time and sound are not separated by “stable” matter, and the ideality of the music – that means its belonging to the sphere of ideas - is directly expressed.

The abolition of the visible separation between inner and outer underlines the presence of the external world in the consciousness. It highlights what Martin Heidegger called “involvement”. This implies that acousmatic music reaches the inmost Being. For these reasons acousmatic music, born from phenomenology, will find a strong echo in the theories developed by Heidegger in *Being and time*, and justifies its use. According to him, Being is not just a Being but a Being-in. He asks the question:

4 “Tout objet sonore figuratif est de toutes façons excessivement abstrait ; lorsqu’il est abs-trait, c’est à dire tiré de son contexte.” BAYLE François, “Points de vue de musiciens”, *Le pouvoir des sons*, cahiers recherche/musique, INA/GRM, 1978, p.257

5 HEGEL Georg Wilhelm Friedrich, *Aesthetics, Lecture on fine arts*, Vol II, translated by T. M. Knox, Oxford at the Clarendon press, 1975, p. 904

“Being-in is not a characteristic that is effected, or even just elicited, in a present-at-hand subject by the 'world's' Being-present-at-hand; Being-in is rather an essential kind of Being of this entity itself. But in that case, what else is presented with this phenomenon than the commercium which is present-at-hand between a subject present-at-hand and an Object present-at-hand?”⁶

Following his answers, we will consider acousmatic music in relation with the “worldhood”, the “understanding”, and the “thrownness”.

3. Acousmatic and Dasein

To say it quickly, what Heidegger calls Dasein is Being confronted with existence. For this reason, all human actions are necessarily an expression of Dasein. Our purpose is to show the specific connections between Dasein and acousmatic music due to its invisibility.

3.1. Worldhood

“When an entity within-the-world has already been proximally freed for its Being, that Being is its "involvement". With any such entity as entity, there is some involvement.”⁷

Consciousness is inseparable from the consciousness of the world. But this consciousness is not pure consciousness and already has certain characteristics. Among these characteristics, we will consider “reference and signs”, “state-of-mind” and “significance” in relation with acousmatic music.

3.1.1. Reference and signs

According to Heidegger the consciousness of the word is inseparable from its significance because Dasein already sees the use he can do of it as ready-to-hand matter or as reference: all sort of sounds are ready-to-hand matter and symbols. We have already seen that recorded sounds had a nature of sign, due to the disengagement. This mechanism inherently belongs to Dasein: “Signs also arise when one takes as a sign [Zum-Zeichen-nehmen] something that is ready-to-hand already.”⁸ In acousmatic music, sounds from raw material as well as sounds from all sorts of tools can be used, and sound itself is considered as material. Among all the symbols it carries, the music and more particularly acousmatic music, being invisible, meets the notion of invisibility, that is both the world of the invisible spirit and the symbol of all that is invisible. Invisibility becomes ready-to-hand.

3.1.2. State-of-mind

The state-of-mind is not considered as something that affects the Being after the fact, following the flow of existence. On the contrary, “State-of-mind is one of the existential structures in

⁶ HEIDEGGER Martin, *Being and time*, translated by John Macquarrie & Edward Robinson, Blackwell, Oxford, 1962, p. 170

⁷ Op. cit. p. 116

⁸ Op. cit. p. 111

which the Being of the “there” maintains itself”.⁹ Mood is essential in Dasein’s meeting with the world and the music, that is often said to express feelings, has also this deepness; mood and feelings have a link even if are not the same thing. Mood enables “to direct one-self toward something”, and first of all toward the question of his existence:

“... the mood brings Dasein before the "that-it-is" of its "there", which, as such, stares it in the face with the inexorability of an enigma.”¹⁰

The affects push Dasein placed before the contingency of its existence to understand this enigma, inevitably invisible. The invisibility of acousmatic sounds, due to invisibility of their cause and to the disengagement, expresses this enigma and involves the consciousness on the path of understanding.

Besides, Vincent Tiffon wrote:

“Because the recorded sound is invisible and in this way opposes the sound of the concert which is visible, we fall into the domain of the body, of the affect, and of the real presence of the body.”¹¹

If instrumental music also plays on the affects, the intimacy resulting from the invisibility of the causes displaces the sensation of movement towards the felt and the interiority. This real presence is not limited to sensation, a consciousness placed before the fact of its existence on a primitive level, essentially carried by emotions. This presence is also not that of organic functions replayed by pulsation. The acting body, the external, biological body of the instrumentalist, in its disappearance, reveals the “inner” body, the one who is at one with the world when he feels and perceives himself. This sensation of being drives Dasein to understanding because “Understanding always has its mood”¹². And understanding implies significance.

3.1.3. Significance

The possibility of signification doesn’t come after the meeting of the entity with the external world, but already exists in Dasein:

“The "for-the-sake-of-which" signifies an "in-order-to"; this in turn, a "towards-this"; the latter, an "in-which" of letting something be involved; and that in turn, the "with-which" of an involvement. These relationships are bound up with one another as a primordial totality; they are what they are as this signifying [Be-deuten) in which Dasein gives itself beforehand its Being-in-the-world as something to be understood. The relational totality of this signifying we call "significance".”¹³

We saw above that invisibility can be ready-to-hand and a sign. By the significance, the “in-order-to” of the invisibility can be the “for-the-sake” of invisible. We touch here a very important point: as the material, the sound, is invisible, the invisible becomes the material of acousmatic music. That means that not only the matter, the sound, is invisible, but also that the

⁹ Op. cit. p. 182

¹⁰Ibid. p. 175

¹¹ <https://revues.mshparisnord.fr:443/filigrane/index.php/js/lodel/docannexe/file/652/index.php?id=92>.

¹² HEIDEGGER Martin, *Being and Time*, p. 182

¹³ Op. cit. p. 120

invisible becomes the main topic of acousmatic music. Among all these invisibilities, we will only consider the ones in relation with Dasein.

We can find in Pierre Henry's *Variations pour une porte et un soupir* an excellent example of acousmatic's worldhood: he uses sounds from a flexatone, that is an instrument, from a door, that is a tool, and from breathe – the more invisible of all – that is manifestation of life. These elements, taken from all categories of sounds (natural, tool, instrumental), are both sonic material and symbols of what human being can meet in his life. The main character, the door, is a symbol of transition and always have its "mood". It underlines the use of ready-to-hand sonic matter as reference. Considering the title of different movements (sommeil, éveil, fièvre, mort...), the entire piece sounds like an allegory of the enigma of life.

3.2. Understanding

According to Heidegger, understanding is made of interpretation, circumspection and sight. A lot of arts and a lot of human actions imply opposite sights, and this is not a particularity of acousmatic music. But acousmatic music reflects these invisible sights by its complete invisibility. For example, we can mention: I and you, nature and nurture, content and form, the work itself and what it represents, understanding and feeling... All these oppositions are well known, and we will not discuss further on them. But it is interesting, concerning our purpose, to see what sort of understanding and what sort of sights imply the "démarche concrète", at the origin of acousmatic music, which goes from hearing to doing, and from perception to abstraction.

We might think that Heidegger has condemned before time the reduced listening: "It requires a very artificial and complicated frame of mind to "hear" a "pure noise"."¹⁴ But we have already seen that sounds can be used as ready-to-hand and as symbols. The reduced listening aims at revealing sound features in order to create a coherent musical architecture. This is the situation described under the name of "understanding": "In the "for-the-sake-of-which", existing Being-in-the-world is disclosed as such, and this disclosedness we have called "understanding"."¹⁵ In order to analyze what kind of understanding involves the "démarche concrète" in relation with the invisible, we will resort to the *Phenomenology of spirit* by Hegel. We will study the transition from perception to understanding, the "rational instinct" and the opposition between natural consciousness and real knowledge.

3.2.1. Perception and understanding

The "for-the-sake-of-which" suppose the perception of "the ready-to-hand". According to Hegel:

"If, namely, we look back to the movement of perceiving and to that of the Understanding, in which the latter reflects itself into itself, and thereby determines its object, we see that the Understanding does not, in that movement, have before itself in its object the relation of these abstract determinations of universal and

14 Op. cit. p. 207 Here Heidegger is talking about discourse, but discourse can also be recorded and being material of a musical piece.

15 Op. cit. 182

individual, essential and external: it is itself the transition, which does not become objective to it.”¹⁶

The transition from perception to understanding is invisible. This invisibility fully belongs to acousmatic music and is constitutive of its apparition and of its way of development. But the work is not a given object: it is an object created by a thought which splits itself in two and borrows a double passage. The transition from perception to understanding that globally grasps an object, and the transition from perception to understanding that places the object in a structure, seizes its various physical properties to organize them in an architecture. Who knows what sights invisibly appear or disappear in these transitions?

3.2.2. Rational instinct

Always according to Hegel:

“The instinct of Reason, on the other hand, is at the same time self-consciousness; but because it is only instinct it is put on one side over against consciousness, in which it has its antithesis. Its satisfaction is, therefore, shattered by this antithesis; it does indeed find itself, viz. the End, and likewise this End as a Thing. But firstly, the End is for that instinct *outside* of the thing presenting itself as End. Secondly, this End, *qua* End, is also *objective*, and therefore does not fall within the observing consciousness itself, but in another intelligence.”¹⁷

What he calls “rational instinct” can only be reached thought its sights, but always stays itself out of consciousness. If we compare instrumental music and acousmatic music, we can see that instrumental music carries this rationality in itself: notes are the result of rational and mathematical operations. The part of instinct is diminished. On the contrary, acousmatic music, using raw sounds and, when composing, being a there and back between hearing and doing shows this invisible instinct and its result which is a rational construction. Besides, recorded soundscapes, among all sorts of pieces, can illustrate this opposition, and more generally, all kind of opposite sights.

For example, we can find in Trevor Wishart’s Red Bird booklet the illustration of these opposite sights: “entire landscapes (such as the garden and the universal factory) act as dynamic symbols, realities in conflict with one another”¹⁸. Among many opposite sights, we can easily recognize here nature and nurture, content and form, the work itself and what it represents, the transition from hearing to doing/understanding, rational instinct and so on... Being acousmatic, this piece also expresses the invisibilities contained in these oppositions.

3.2.3. Natural consciousness and real knowledge

Understanding itself can be considered from two points of view. In his comment on *Phenomenology of spirit*’s introduction, Heidegger wrote:

“Out of principle this view is one-sided, for natural representation always sees only one side (which for it is not even a side, but rather the entirety), the side of things

16G. HEGEL Georg Wilhelm Friedrich, *Phenomenology of Spirit*, translated by A. V. Miller, Oxford University Press, 1977, p. 167

17 Op. cit. p. 157

18 WISHART Trevor, *Red Bird* booklet, Electronic Music Foundation, New York, 2000

that meet it outright. Natural consciousness never looks on the other side, never looks to the being of beings.”¹⁹

In other terms, natural representation believes that what appears is the real. By this fact, the real stays invisible. In order to reach the real:

“We thus restore to the word "skepsis" its original meaning: σκέψις signifies the seeing [Sehen], watching [Zusehen], inspecting [Besehen], that oversees [nachsieht] what and how beings are as beings.”²⁰

It is interesting to notice that, concerning the skepsis, we can read in the Greek-English lexicon by Henry Liddell & Robert Scott, as third meaning: doubt²¹. This transition from seeing to doubt is the ancient Greek ἐποχή (epoché)’s definition. Even if this definition is different from Husserl’s definition, this word carries its history with it, and Husserl choose it knowing it. Besides, it highlights the stand by of the visible to reach an invisible real at first sight²². That is what acousmatic music is doing. Acousmatic music is telling us: what *is* doesn’t appear as such, and it doesn’t appear because what *is* is in the consciousness. What appears at first sight must be put aside. From this point of view acousmatic music materializes the “skepsis”. The ancient and the new epoché work together, in stereo, “off the beaten track”.

Composers and works are the place of all sorts of invisible sights. Of course these sights are invisibly existing in all the arts, but they are expressed in their characteristic of invisibility in acousmatic music. By this way of being that materialize the abolition of inner and outer, it expresses the way of being of Dasein’s understanding.

3.3. Thrownness

Thrownness means that Dasein has been thrown in the world without having decided it. It has several implications; among them, we will study the question of the origin, the one of the solitude and the one of the death, in relation with invisibility.

3.3.1. Origin

“This characteristic of Dasein's Being- this 'that it is'- is veiled in its "whence" and "whither", yet disclosed in itself all the more unveiledly; we call it the "thrownness" of this entity into its "there"”²³

Like Dasein, recorded sounds are veiled in their whence and direction. Even if we know the conditions under which the composer made his recordings, even if we guess the objects he used, on the one hand the reality of these objects, and on the other hand his deep motives and unconscious intentions remain hidden. They are thrown in our ears.

19 HEIDEGGER Martin, “Hegel’s concept of experience”, *Off the beaten track*, translated and edited by Julian Young and Kenneth Haynes, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2002, p. 117

20 Op. cit. p. 114

21 Of course, we can read the same definitions in the dictionary Grec-Français Bailly.

22 In this case, by watching and watching again.

23 HEIDEGGER Martin, *Being and Time*, p. 174

But not only: the Being-thrown exists without being the cause of his existence, and without knowing this cause, like acousmatic sounds. The pure invisibility of acousmatic music expresses the pure invisibility of the causes of thrownness.

3.3.2. “Nothing of the world”

The Being-thrown discovers himself like a stranger in the world:

“Uncanniness reveals itself authentically in the state-of-mind of anxiety; and, as the most elemental way in which thrown Dasein is disclosed, it puts Dasein's Being-in-the-world face to face with the "nothing" of the world ; in the face of this "nothing", Dasein is anxious with anxiety about its ownmost potentiality-for-Being”²⁴.

The nothing of the world means that, in fact, we are nothing for the world, that it can exist without us and that there is no meaning external to us in it. The matter there, under our eyes, the matter that makes the world and that we use, the matter that we depend on, the very matter that we are made of, is not there for us. It moves with its own movement, is indifferent to our existence and does not guarantee it in any way. In this meaning, the visible matter is removed from us in the same way than from acousmatic sounds. By bringing the music back into complete invisibility, by denying the negation of the invisible present in instrumental music, the acousmatic reveals an irrational and a given that the view of the musicians-for-us, and of the matter, hides. The codified human treatment of the visible matter in instrumental music masks the nothingness of the world. On the contrary, acousmatic music, by the use of a material that is hidden from view, leaves the listener facing himself and his loneliness, and reveals the “nothing of the world”.

3.3.3. Death

On the path from the “nothing of the world” to the nothing of being, we meet the death, the ultimate and definitive invisible.

Death is not what “Dasein procures for itself subsequently and occasionally in the course of its Being. On the contrary, if Dasein exists, it has already been thrown into this possibility.”²⁵

The consciousness of a never ending time makes our finiteness more cruel. It belongs ontologically to Dasein and gives its responsibility to him. Finiteness means that the death does not come like an external event, but is a full part of Dasein. This has two implications: firstly life is like sounds whose way of being is appearing by disappearing. Inexorably, a musical piece and sounds are destined to end right from their beginning. The possibility to fix sounds on a support doesn't change anything: each replay only replays this reality again and again.

“... death reveals itself as that possibility which is one's ownmost, which is non-relational, and which is not to be outstripped [unuberholbare].”²⁶ 294

²⁴ Op. cit. p. 321

²⁵ Op. cit. p. 295

²⁶ Op. cit. p. 294

Secondly, at the opposite of instrumental music, there is no possibility in acousmatic music to make the piece longer by an external agent, by slowing down the tempo or by improvising. The end of an acousmatic piece only depends on itself, its duration is fixed on a support in the same movement than the piece itself, and is non-relational and not to be outstripped. It perfectly reflects the invisible ending time contained in Dasein.

4. Conclusion

Music is invisible and expresses invisible symbols and sights; but these invisibilities are veiled by many things visible in an instrumental concert. On the contrary, acousmatic music has the extraordinary power to express all these invisibilities in their characteristic of invisibility. This way, it is speaking of all the invisibilities inside human being and of the enigma of his existence.

The abolition of the distinction between inner and outer in acousmatic music, due to its complete invisibility, from this point of view, reflects the worldhood of Dasein more than another art. For this reason acousmatic music is not only an important innovation concerning musical material and grammar. It is also a philosophical innovation in the arts. Acousmatic music is a privileged expression of Dasein that gives it its particular deepness, and can be considered as a particularly “existential” art.

5. References

- BAYLE François, *Musique acousmatique, propositions, positions*, Buchet/Chastel, Paris, 1993
- BAYLE François, “Points de vue de musiciens”, *Le pouvoir des sons*, cahiers recherche/musique, INA/GRM, 1978,
- GREIMAS Algirdas Julien, CORTES Joseph, *Dictionnaire raisonné du langage*, Hachette Supérieur, Paris, 1993
- HEGEL Georg Wilhelm Friedrich, *Aesthetics, Lecture on fine arts*, Vol II, translated by T. M. Knox, Oxford at the Clarendon press, 1975
- HEGEL Georg Wilhelm Friedrich, *Phenomenology of Spirit*, translated by A. V. Miller, Oxford University Press, 1977
- HEIDEGGER Martin, *Being and time*, translated by John Macquarrie & Edward Robinson, Blackwell, Oxford, 1962
- HEIDEGGER Martin, “Hegel’s concept of experience”, *Off the beaten track*, translated and edited by Julian Young and Kenneth Haynes, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2002
- HENRY Pierre, *Variations pour une porte et un soupir*, harmonia mundi, Arles, 1987
- TIFFON Vincent, “L’image sonore: la présence invisible”
<https://revues.mshparisnord.fr:443/filigrane/index.php/js/lodel/docannexe/file/652/index.php?id=92>.
- WISHART Trevor, *Red Bird*, Electronic Music Foundation, New York, 2000